

TO STUDY THE EFFICACY OF PRIMARY CLOSURE OF COMMON BILE DUCT FOLLOWING CHOLEDOCHOLITHOTOMY

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Abstract

- In the current era , CBD stone management is by endoscopic approach,however, due to nonavailability and non-affordability, few patients are considered for the open surgical technique (choledocholithotomy)
- In the past, following open surgery CBD incision was closed over T Tube which has some amount of morbidity
- Presently few recent references from the literature mention that closure of CBD without T Tube / Biliary stenting is safer and carries less morbidity
- In this current study, this technique of primary closure is considered in our institute following approval from the ethical committee
- Till now we have completed 5 patients and got encouraging results which are presented in today's presentation

INTRODUCTION

- Obstruction of the common bile duct due to presence of large and leftover stones after ERCP has been corrected by opening the common bile duct and removing the stones.
- There are some ways to close common bile ducts like
 - Closure over T tube
 - Closure over Biliary stent
 - Primary closure of CBD

Advantages of primary closure of CBD

- Permits early removal of the abdominal drain
- The patient has a smoother postoperative course, with less pain and an earlier return to work
- Avoids T-tube-related complications
- Additional procedure of biliary stent removal is not required

- The common bile duct can be closed safely by primary suture with minimal risk of leakage
- Hence the topic of primary closure of common bile duct is taken for the research

AIM

- **TO STUDY EFFICACY OF PRIMARY CLOSURE OF COMMON BILE DUCT FOLLOWING CHOLEDOCHOLITHOTOMY**

OBJECTIVES

- 1 To find incidence of bile leakage postoperatively
- 2 To study the duration of postoperative hospital stay and early recovery of patient .

METHODS AND MATERIAL

- **Study Center** -Dr. Vithalrao Vikhe Patil Foundation's Medical College and Hospital, Ahmednagar
- **Study Population-** All the patients with CBD stones
- **Study Type-** Prospective observational study
- **Study duration** –12 months (August 2022 to August 2023)

- **INCLUSION CRITERIA**

- Age- 18 to 80
- Accepted for anaesthesia
- Patients with CBD stones

- **EXCLUSION CRITERIA**

- Not fit for surgery

Method and material

- All patients posted for choledocholithiasis were selected with informed consent for the open-operative procedure (choledocholithotomy)
- The stones are mobilized to a supraduodenal portion of CBD and opened longitudinally
- The stones in the common bile duct are extracted.
- An Intraoperative cholangiogram is planned to confirm the free flow of bile in the duodenum. Incision over CBD sutured without T Tube/ Intrahepatic stent.
- Cholecystectomy done
- Procedure completed after placing an abdominal drain in GB fossa

Assessment Parameters

Preoperative parameters:

- Sex,
- Age,
- Liver function indices,
- USG Abdomen pelvis
- MRCP
- CECT Abdomen pelvis
- CBD Diameter
- Number of CBD stones
- GB status

Intraoperative parameters:

- Operation time
- Intraoperative Cholangiogram finding

Postoperative parameters:

- Hospital stay,
- Liver function indices
- Drain removal time
- Complications - cholangitis , biliary leak

Follow-up parameters:

- LFT
- Residual CBD stones
- Stone recurrence
- Stricture

Observation and result

	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4	Case 5
AGE/SEX	35/MALE	80/MALE	46/FEMALE	72/FEMALE	55/MALE
CBD NO. OF STONE STONE SIZE	5 CALCULI 15 MM	SINGLE 12MM	SINGLE 6MM	MULTIPLE 21MM(CBD 26)	SINGLE 14 MM
GB STATUS	STONE+ WITH DISTENTION	NORMAL	12 MM STONE +	DISTENDED 6mm STONE	STONE +
LFT-TB/DB/IB	4.2/2.1/2	3.2/2/1.2	5/3/3	4.2/2.2/1.4	3.5/2.4/1.4
INTRAOP TIME	2 HOUR	2 ½ HR	2 HOUR	3 HOUR	2 HOUR
DRAIN REMOVED	POD-3	POD-4	POD3	POD-3	POD-4
HOSPITAL STAY	POD-7	POD-9	POD-8	POD-7	POD-7
BILIARY LEAK	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
RESIDUAL STONES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
RECURRENCE	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO

	Case 6	Case 7	Case 8	Case 9	Case 10
AGE/SEX	35 /MALE	75/female	40/FEMALE	68/MALE	55/MALE
CBD NO. OF STONE STONE SIZE	3 CALCULI 8 MM	SINGLE 8MM	SINGLE 8 MM	MULTIPLE 21MM(CBD 26)	SINGLE 14 MM
GB STATUS	STONE+ WITH DISTENTION	15 mm stone	12 MM STONE +	DISTENDED 3mm STONE	STONE +
LFT-TB/DB/IB	4.2/2.1/2	3.1/1.9/1.2	4.3/3/3	4.2/2.2/1.4	3.5/2.4/1.4
INTRAOP TIME	2 HOUR	2 ½ HR	2 HOUR	3 HOUR	2 HOUR
DRAIN REMOVED	POD-3	POD-4	POD3	POD-3	POD-4
HOSPITAL STAY	POD-7	POD-9	POD8	POD-7	POD-7
BILIARY LEAK	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
RESIDUAL STONES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
RECURRENCE	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO

- In a current study, 10 patients are studied
- Our patients for whom primary closure was performed ranged in age from 22 to 90 years .
- The hospital stay ranged from 7 to 10 days.
- In all patients drain was removed on 3rd /4th postoperative day
- There is no evidence of postoperative surgical site infection
- No delayed complications / residual / recurrent stones was detected

DISCUSSION

- The technique of CBD closure over T tube is practiced from beginning of choledocholithotomy
- T tube inherits the complications and morbidities.
- With availability of Endoscopic Retrograde Choledocho-Pancreatography (ERCP) there is paradigm change in the management of biliary stones.
- Following ERCP, There are some patients with residual stones, hence for such cases , we need exploration of CBD.
- In our region, due to non availability and non affordability of ERCP, patients subjected for the open surgical technique for the management of stones
- To reduce morbidity this technique of primary closure attempted by us

And till now we are getting encouraging results

CONCLUSION

- The current study of primary closure following choledocholithotomy is found to be safe and beneficial to the patients with less comorbidity and postop complications

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